

Effects of water extracts of *Equisetum arvense* and *Gongronema latifolium* leaves on egg hatching of *Meloidogyne incognita*

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Abstract: Root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are among the most damaging plant-parasitic nematodes limiting crop production in Nigeria. Their control has largely relied on synthetic chemicals which pose health and environmental challenges. This has resulted in the search and development of alternatives to synthetic chemicals for nematode control. This study investigated the effects of water extracts of *Equisetum arvense* and *Gongronema latifolium* leaves on the egg hatching of *Meloidogyne incognita* under *in vitro* conditions. Water extracts were prepared at concentrations of 25,000 mg/kg and 50,000 mg/kg and applied to freshly extracted nematode eggs. Observations on egg hatch were recorded for 14 days. The results showed that water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* leaves significantly inhibited egg hatching of *M. incognita*, with *E. arvense* at 50,000 mg/kg giving the highest egg-hatch reduction percentage (43.92%). The findings suggest that water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* leaves could be useful in managing root-knot nematode infestations in vegetable fields.

Keywords: *Equisetum arvense*, *Gongronema latifolium*, *Meloidogyne incognita*, Nematicidal activity, Phytochemicals, Water extracts

Introduction

Poor yield of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) in Nigeria has been attributed to several biotic

factors, including nematode diseases (Vicente *et al.*, 2022). *Meloidogyne* spp. infection has been reported as one of the limiting factors in groundnut cultivation, which in some areas

results in 90–100% yield loss. Groundnut infected with root-knot nematodes has been reported to show stunted growth, yield loss, conspicuous galls on roots, and distortions on groundnut pods (Kavita *et al.*, 2023).

Chemical nematicide is one of the fastest and most effective nematode control methods, but they are detrimental to both humans and the environment and are relatively unaffordable to the average small-scale farmer (Adeogun *et al.*, 2025). Therefore, there is a need to develop alternative control methods that are cheap, environmentally friendly, and safe for human health. The use of botanicals is one of the promising alternative methods for nematode control (Desmedt *et al.*, 2020). Among such botanicals are water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium*, which are reported to exhibit nematicidal activities based on observations of low nematode populations in areas where they grow naturally.

Many botanical extracts have been found to contain phytochemicals such as alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, diterpenes, glucosinolates, acetylenes, and thienyls, which are known to act against plant-parasitic nematodes (Desmedt *et al.*, 2020; Faria *et al.*, 2021). These findings suggest that plant extracts can be useful in reducing nematode

populations and potentially reduce the use of synthetic nematicides in nematode-infested soils. Against this background, this study was conducted to evaluate the effects of water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* on the egg hatch of *M. incognita in vitro*.

Materials and Method

Study area

This study was carried out in the Department of Crop Science Laboratory, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

Sources of seeds and plant materials

Seeds of groundnut (*A. hypogaea*) susceptible to *Meloidogyne incognita* were collected from the Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR), Samaru, Zaria, Nigeria. Leaves of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* were collected from the wild and identified in the Department of Biology, UAES.

Production of Meloidogyne incognita inoculum

Pure cultures of *M. incognita* were maintained on *Celosia argentea* cv. TLV8 in the nematode culture plot of the Department of Crop Science, UAES, for seven weeks. The identity of *M. incognita* was confirmed by examining the perineal pattern of adult

females as described by Eisenback *et al.* (1981).

Preparation of plant extracts

Water extracts were prepared using the method of Adekunle and Fawole (2003). Ten grams of each leaf sample were placed in 100 ml of distilled water and heated in a water bath at 100°C for one hour. The mixture was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The stock solution (100,000 mg/kg) was diluted to obtain 50,000 and 25,000 mg/kg concentrations.

Extraction of M. incognita eggs

Roots of *C. argentea* plants infected with *M. incognita* were washed and cut into 2-cm pieces. Eggs were extracted using the sodium hypochlorite (chlorox) method (Ravichandra, 2010). The egg suspension was collected through sieving, rinsed, and diluted in water. Aliquots of the egg suspension were pipetted and counted under a dissecting microscope.

Application of extracts and experimental design

Aliquots of 6 ml of each extract concentration (25,000 mg/kg and 50,000 mg/kg) and distilled water (control) were dispensed into Petri dishes containing approximately 300 *M. incognita* eggs. Treatments included water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* at two concentrations each and distilled water. The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four replications. Incubation was done at room temperature, and egg hatch counts were taken every 24 hours for 14 days under a dissecting microscope.

Statistical analysis

Data were log-transformed [$\log_{10}(x + 1)$] and analyzed using ANOVA (PROC GLM, SAS 2001). Means were separated using Fisher's LSD at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Effects of water extracts of *Equisetum arvense* and *Gongronema latifolium* leaves on egg hatching of *Meloidogyne incognita*

Treatment	Concentration (mg/kg)	% Egg Hatch(EH) in 14 days	% Egg Hatch Reduction (EHR) in 14 days
<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	40,000	33.67	43.92
<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	20,000	46.83	32.50
<i>Gongronema latifolium</i>	40,000	39.00	40.75
<i>Gongronema latifolium</i>	20,000	47.25	34.92
Water (control)	-	79.75	0
LSD _{0.05}		4.99	6.32

Each value is a mean of four replicates.

The results of this study indicate that water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* leaves reduced egg-hatch of *M. incognita* in the in vitro study; *E. arvense* at 50,000 mg/kg gave 43.92% reduction which was the highest, *E. arvense* at 20,000 mg/kg gave 32.50% reduction, *G. latifolium* at 50,000mg/kg gave 40.75% reduction, *G. latifolium* at 20,000mg/kg gave 34.92% reduction and water gave 0% reduction. Similar results have been reported by a number of authors. Adegbite (2011) found that bitter leaf extract inhibited the egg of root-knot nematode when applied at a concentration of 2.5% w/v, i.e., 250g per 10 liters of water. The reduced egg hatch in treated eggs could be as a result of nematicidal activities of the biotic compounds in leaves of the botanicals used in this study.

The observed reduction in egg hatch can be attributed to the presence of phytochemicals in *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium*. These plants have been reported to contain a number of phytochemicals that have been reported to be toxic to a number of pathogens, including plant-parasitic nematodes (Barbosa *et al.*, 2024). Equisetonin and quercetin have been isolated from *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* respectively, and both have been reported to kill plant-parasitic nematodes (Faria *et al.*, 2021; Barbosa *et al.*, 2024). These substances

might have prevented the eggs of the nematode from hatching into juveniles.

Furthermore, the efficacy of these plant extracts in reducing egg hatch could be due to the disruption of nematode enzymatic activities or interference with embryonic development within the eggs. The concentration-dependent response observed in this study suggests that the nematicidal compounds in *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* extracts are effective at higher concentrations, which is consistent with findings from other studies on plant-based nematicides.

The potential of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* as sources of natural nematicides is promising, given their availability and the growing need for environmentally friendly alternatives to synthetic nematicides. Further research could focus on isolating and characterizing the specific compounds responsible for the observed nematicidal activity, as well as evaluating the efficacy of these extracts under field conditions.

Conclusion

Water extracts of *E. arvense* and *G. latifolium* at 25,000 and 50,000 mg/kg significantly inhibited egg hatch of *M. incognita* under *in vitro* conditions. The extract of *E. arvense* at 50,000 mg/kg gave the highest reduction in

egg hatch (43.92%), while *G. latifolium* at 25,000 mg/kg gave the lowest (32.50%) among the treatments but still significantly better than the control. These findings suggest that water extracts of these botanicals could serve as effective biocontrol agents for root-knot nematode infestations in vegetable fields.

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